

Maternal Hypovitaminosis D Presenting as Late-Onset Hypocalcemic Seizure in a Term Neonate: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

High prevalence of Vitamin D deficiency and its potential effects on human health is a growing concern around the world. Among pregnant women, it can have serious consequences for both mother and baby. Several studies have shown vitamin D deficiency as predisposing risk factor to preeclampsia and gestational diabetes mellitus in the mother^[1,2]. When a mother has low levels of vitamin D during pregnancy, it can lead to insufficient transfer to the fetus, resulting in low stores in the newborn^[3]. This deficiency in newborns can cause low calcium levels, which might present as anything from no symptoms to tremors, in more severe cases, seizures due to hypocalcemia. Although it's a less frequently reported condition, hypocalcemic seizures in newborns can indeed be linked to maternal vitamin D deficiency.

Key words: Hypocalcemia; Late onset; Seizure; Vitamin D deficiency; Case report

INTRODUCTION

The incidence of hypocalcemic seizures ranges from 1.1% to 22 % with hypocalcemia and hypoglycemia being the most common metabolic causes^[4]. We present a case of a 10 day old neonate born to a mother with a maternal history of Gestational diabetes mellitus presenting with neonatal seizure secondary to hypocalcemia. The biochemical abnormality that was observed in both the neonate and mother was low Vitamin D levels, high Parathyroid hormone and hypocalcemia both in the mother and the neonate.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 10-day old baby was referred from primary center to the tertiary care facility due to refractory hypocalcemic seizures. The baby was born to a 31-year-old primigravida from a non consanguineous marriage following a spontaneous conception. Antenatal scans were normal. Mother had Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (GDM), and was managed with insulin and oral hypoglycemic agents. Baby was delivered via Lower segment cesarean section(LSCS). Baby cried at birth, received routine care and was monitored in Neonatal intensive care unit for one day for asymptomatic hypoglycemia which improved with feeds. The baby's blood group is O positive and her serologies test are protective. The baby was discharged on day 4 of life. In day 6 of life, the baby experienced around 10 episodes of tonic-clonic seizures, each lasting for a few seconds. MRI brain done on the same day was normal. The baby's seizures persisted, prompting the initiation of antiepileptics (levetiracetam, Clobazam). Baby's calcium levels were low and intravenous(IV) calcium was initiated and later switched over to oral calcium. Both ultrasound abdomen and cranium ultrasound were normal. The calcium levels improved, and the baby remained seizure free for the next 24 hours, and was discharged on day 9 of life with calcium and vitamin D supplements.

However on day 10 of life, the baby had a recurrence of seizures and was referred to the tertiary care center for further management. On clinical examination on day 10 the baby was active, alert, neurologically normal with stable vitals. Initial blood investigations showed normal CBC, CRP, but low ionized calcium levels (2.7 mg/dl). Further workup for hypocalcemia revealed elevated phosphorus (10.8 mg/dl), normal alkaline phosphatase(ALP), low 25 hydroxyvitamin D (10.2 ng/ml), mildly elevated parathyroid hormone (PTH) (98.7 pg/ml) and borderline low magnesium (1.4 mg/dl). Urea, creatinine were normal, Urine calcium-to-creatinine ratio was 0.2.

Baby was started on IV calcium at 50 mg/kg/day. On the second day of admission the baby had 3 episodes of seizures and was continued on antiepileptics. A Pediatric endocrinologist was consulted. Baby was started on oral cholecalciferol and calcitriol. The IV calcium was increased to 70 mg/kg/day and a single dose of IV magnesium was given. Mother's lab investigations showed borderline low calcium, normal phosphorus, low 25-hydroxyvitamin D, mildly elevated PTH and normal magnesium, indicating Vitamin D deficiency with secondary hyperparathyroidism.

Repeat ionized calcium values showed an improving trend. Baby did not experience further seizures. On day 4 of admission, the baby was switched over to oral calcium supplements and oral Levetiracetam was discontinued as the baby was neurologically normal. By day 8 of admission, ionized calcium levels had normalized, phosphorus levels were declining and vitamin D levels improved with calcitriol. Patient was asked to follow up

after two weeks with calcium and phosphorus, Thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH) and T4 levels after 2 weeks which were subsequently normal.

DISCUSSION

Vitamin D deficiency during pregnancy and lactation is an important risk for rickets which is very well established^[5]. However, there has been only a few reports regarding hypocalcemic seizure secondary to vitamin D deficiency. Vitamin D deficiency is defined by 25(OH)D levels less than 20 ng/ml or < 50 nmol/ml with a estimated prevalence in maternal mothers ranging from 9% to 40%^[6]. Similarly an Indian study showed 25(OH)D levels 17.5±10.30 and 79.5% of mothers had less than 25 nmol/ml^[7]. Vitamin D levels in the mother are directly linked to Vitamin D levels in the neonate. So, if the mother is Vitamin D deficient the newborn is likely to be deficient due to reduced placental transfer of Vitamin D^[3]. Reduced vitamin D levels in blood as well as breast milk can predispose to Vitamin D deficiency and late onset neonatal hypocalcemia^[5].

The causes of late onset neonatal hypocalcemia includes excessive phosphate intake, hypomagnesemia, hypoparathyroidism and vitamin D deficiency^[8]. In our case, there has been no reports of cow's milk consumption leading to high phosphate load. Hypocalcemia and hypoglycemia could point towards Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) as cause of hypocalcemia but it usually presents in the first few days of life and does not present with resistant seizures. Low magnesium was reported and was treated with iv magnesium sulfate. High phosphorus levels could point to Pseudohypoparathyroidism but low Vitamin D levels rules that out. The hyperphosphatemia could be explained by resistance to Parathyroid hormone in bone secondary to Vitamin D deficiency^[9].

Ruling out other potential causes of late onset hypocalcemia in our case, with reduced 25(OH) levels in mother and elevated phosphorus, low 25 OH Vitamin D ,mildly elevated PTH in the neonate suggests that Vitamin D deficiency could be the possible cause. The main takeaway for this case is that if a neonate experiences treatment resistant seizures secondary to hypocalcemia, Vitamin D deficiency should be an important differential that should be evaluated. A study conducted in Spain, found that even with multivitamin supplementation including 200 IU/day of vitamin D, 63% of pregnant women have insufficient vitamin D levels and 26% deficient levels^[10]. Furthermore, a key question is if Vitamin D supplementation in deficient mothers could prevent this condition and there has been no sufficient data to make this claim.

CONCLUSION

In neonates presenting with late onset hypocalcemic seizures that are resistant to treatment maternal and fetal Vitamin D levels should be evaluated after ruling out the common causes.

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DECLARATION

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